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Дані про авторів

Сафонова Віра Євгенівна,

д.е.н., професор, професор кафедри підприємництва, торгівлі та біржової діяльності, Київський кооперативний інститут бізнесу і права, м. Київ, Україна

Бучнів Максим Михайлович,

к.е.н., доцент, доцент кафедри публічного управління, менеджменту та маркетингу, Східноукраїнський національний університет імені В. Даля, Україна

Прокопенко Олексій Володимирович,

к.філ.н., доцент, доцент кафедри філософії, культурології та інформаційної діяльності, Східноукраїнський національний університет ім. В. Даля, Україна

Сергієнко Сергій Сергійович,

фахівець навчально–методичного відділу технологій дистанційного навчання Центру інформаційних технологій в освіті Інституту післядипломної освіти, Національ–

ний технічний університет України «Київський політехнічний інститут імені Ігоря Сікорського», м. Київ, Україна

Data about the authors

Vira Safonova,

Dr. Sc. (Econ), Professor, Professor of the Department of Enterprise, Trade and Stock Exchange Department, Kyiv Cooperative Institute of Business and Law, Kyiv, Ukraine

Maxym Buchniev,

PhD (Econ), Associate Professor, Department of Public Administration, Management and Marketing, Volodymyr Dahl East Ukrainian National University, Ukraine

Oleksii Prokopenko,

PhD in Philosophy, Associate Professor, Associate Professor of the Department of Philosophy, Cultural Studies and Information Activities, Volodymyr Dahl East Ukrainian National University, Ukraine

Serhii Serhiienko,

Specialist of the educational and methodological department of distance learning technologies of the Center for Information Technologies in Education of the Institute of Postgraduate Education, National Technical University of Ukraine «Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute», Kyiv, Ukraine

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KUKSA I.M., LEVKIV H.Ya., TELICHKO N.O.

Modeling of Innovative Cluster Development of Agro–Industrial Complex in the Conditions of Globalization and Digitalization

Relevance of the research topic. *The development of the agro–industrial complex should take place with close interaction between business, government and science. At the same time, the instability of the institutional matrix and rapidly changing processes in the external environment require a solution to the problem of uninterrupted revision of the clustering of agricultural enterprises, taking into account modern trends.*

Formulation of the problem. *There is a need to revise the modeling process of innovative cluster development of the agro–industrial complex in the conditions of globalization and digitalization under the conditions of today.*

Setting the goal and tasks of the research – *modeling of innovative cluster development of the agro–industrial complex in the conditions of globalization and digitalization, taking into account the world experience of forming a market economy based on knowledge.*

Research method or methodology. *The following research methods are used in the article: induction, deduction, economic modeling, statistical observation, abstraction, synthesis and analysis.*

Presentation of the main material (research results). *Indirect state regulation by innovative development of agro–industrial clusters is determined. A model of the formation of an innovative regional center as a reference point and integrator of the functioning of an agro–industrial cluster has been developed. Conceptual guidelines for the formation of participants in an innovative industry cluster are proposed.*

Field of application of results. The results of the research can be used in the practical activities of business entities, institutions of higher education, and local self–government bodies to improve the clustering processes of the agro–industrial complex.

Conclusions according to the article. Our proposed modeling of innovative cluster development of the agro–industrial complex in the conditions of globalization and digitalization will have the following advantages: the possibility of joint use of joint capitals and acceleration of the introduction of innovations; joint use of resources, material and technical support, savings on their acquisition and maintenance; effective specialization of enterprises by region, scope of activity and features of the functioning of each individual agro–industrial complex enterprise, etc.

Keywords: innovation clusters, investment management, digitalization of the economy.

КУКСА І. М., ЛЕВКІВ Г. Я., ТЕЛІЧКО Н. О.

Моделювання інноваційного кластерного розвитку агропромислового комплексу в умовах глобалізації та цифровізації

Актуальність теми дослідження. Розвиток агропромислового комплексу повинен відбуватися при тісній взаємодії бізнесу, влади та науки. Одночасно нестабільність інституціональної матриці та швидкозмінні процеси у зовнішньому середовищі, вимагають вирішення проблематики безперервного перегляду кластеризації агропідприємств з урахуванням сучасних тенденцій.

Постановка проблеми. Існує потреба перегляду процесу моделювання інноваційного кластерного розвитку агропромислового комплексу в умовах глобалізації та цифровізації за умов сьогодення.

Постановка мети і завдань дослідження – моделювання інноваційного кластерного розвитку агропромислового комплексу в умовах глобалізації та цифровізації з урахуванням світового досвіду формування ринкової економіки на основі знань.

Метод або методологія дослідження. У статті використано такі методи дослідження: індукція, дедукція, економічне моделювання, статистичне спостереження, абстракція, синтез та аналіз.

Презентація основного матеріалу (результати дослідження). Визначено опосередковане державне регулювання інноваційним розвитком агропромислових кластерів. Розроблено модель формування інноваційного регіонального центру як опорної точки та інтегратора функціонування агропромислового кластеру. Запропоновано концептуальні орієнтири формування учасників інноваційного галузевого кластеру.

Галузь застосування результатів. Результати дослідження можуть бути використані в практичній діяльності суб'єктів підприємницької діяльності, закладів вищої освіти, органів місцевого самоврядування для удосконалення процесів кластеризації агропромислового комплексу.

Висновки за статтею. Запропоноване нами моделювання інноваційного кластерного розвитку агропромислового комплексу в умовах глобалізації та цифровізації матиме такі переваги: можливість спільного використання об'єднаних капіталів та прискорення впровадження інновацій; спільне використання ресурсів, матеріально–технічне забезпечення, економія на їх придбанні та утриманні; ефективна спеціалізація підприємств за регіоном, масштабом діяльності та особливостями функціонування кожного окремого підприємства АПК тощо.

Ключові слова: інноваційні кластери, управління інвестиціями, цифровізація економіки.

Problem statement in general and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. Ukraine's focus on the formation of a new type of economy requires modeling the innovative cluster development of the agro–industrial complex and its institutional and legal support. As far as traditional institutional mechanisms cannot be ad–

equated in the process of forming a new technological system based on clustering. The most acceptable for the conditions of Ukraine areas of support for clustering on the innovative path of agro–industrial development may be: institutional and legal support of innovative cluster development; reforming the forms of ownership of institutes of the

innovation sphere, improving the management system and organizational forms of research and design organizations; formation of new innovation institutions (technology parks, research centers, laboratories, etc.), individual or as part of industrial enterprises of research and production complexes and other corporate structures; formation of financial and coordination institutes of innovative development, attraction of institutional investors to the innovative sphere of activity and clusters; regional institutional support for innovative cluster development.

Analysis of the latest research and publications. The problems of cluster partnership were studied by such scientists as: Hnatenko I., Zos-Kior M., Kobets S., Martynov A., Khodakivska O., Bachkir I., Martynova L., Klochan V., Klochan I. and other scientists [1–6]. Valuable for our research are the work of M. Zos-Kio et al., in which the issue of modeling agroclusters with regard to resource saving is raised [7–10]. Progressive cluster modeling methods can be seen in the article I. Gryshchenko et al. [1]. In connection with the expansion of market relations, the analysis of the possibilities of clustering as a specific aspect of the effective functioning of the innovation market, the branching of the innovation infrastructure to increase the role of the state in the implementation of various options for supporting and stimulating innovation activity, the improvement of the economic mechanism, marketing methods for the implementation of this process, acquires special importance in connection with the expansion of market relations. which is indicated in the works of the authors Hnatenko I. et al. [2] and Zos-Kior M. et al. [10] Despite the rather widespread problems of clustering in the scientific world, the question of determining the best models of cluster partnership of the agro-industrial complex under today's conditions, as well as many unexplained problems of financial and investment support for innovative processes in the agricultural sector, remains debatable.

Formulation of the goals of the article (setting the task) – modeling of innovative cluster development of the agro-industrial complex in the conditions of globalization and digitalization, taking into account the world experience of forming a market economy based on knowledge.

Presentation of the main research material with full justification of the obtained sci-

entific results. The state strategy in the field of innovative development of agro-industrial complex taking into account clustering should consist: first, in orientation on direct implementation of measures of national and regional level on increase of qualitative characteristics of Ukrainian scientific and technological potential, intensification of process of mastering scientific knowledge and new technologies. capital; secondly, in encouraging the implementation of innovative activities and investments of innovative directions by agro-industrial entities in order to increase the supply of innovative products, technologies and knowledge; thirdly, in encouraging the demand of economic entities in the field of agro-industrial complex for innovative products, technologies, knowledge, creating favorable conditions for the introduction of innovations in the production and life of the rural population [1–3]. The main directions of improving the mechanism of state regulation of innovation activities of the agro-industrial complex based on clustering can be as follows: improving the current legislation on innovation activities of the agro-industrial complex; improving investment capital and investment image of Ukraine as an agro-industrial state; introduction of the principle of public-private partnership in the innovation sphere of agro-industrial complex; formation of the national innovation system, including the sphere of agro-industrial complex and ensuring its functioning; stimulating the activation of national financial resources, improving public investment in innovative development of agriculture; intensification of attracting foreign investment in agriculture; introduction of complex statistical analysis and evaluation of innovation activity in the agro-industrial complex. Clustering is widespread in European countries (Italy, France, Netherlands, Poland, Switzerland and others). State regulation of innovation activity of the agro-industrial complex based on clustering for European countries is not an accidental phenomenon, as the efficiency of the agro-industrial complex is a constant prerequisite for the prosperity of the whole society. As foreign experience shows, clustering solves a variety of tasks: maintaining prices and incomes of agricultural producers, purposefully creating appropriate conditions for the sale of agricultural products, resource conservation, environmental protection, social support for producers and infrastructure policy for rural areas. Ac-

cordingly, a diverse arsenal of methods and tools is used to implement the strategic goals of effective regulation of the agro-industrial economy on the basis of cluster partnership (induction, deduction, analysis, synthesis, abstraction, modeling, etc.). The analysis of Ukrainian and foreign experience convincingly showed that the formation of

competitive markets and overcoming monopolistic tendencies in the economy is possible only as a result of purposeful activity of institutions of state management of innovation and clustering [5–7].

In order to model the innovative cluster development of agriculture in the context of globalization and digitalization, it is necessary to restruct-

Table 1. World experience and opportunities for cluster adaptation for Ukrainian agro-industrial complex

Country	Features of clustering	Adaptation of perspective clustering measures for Ukrainian agro-industrial complex
Great Britain and Northern Ireland	Objective: to reduce productivity gaps and significant disparities in productivity levels between different regions of the country. Main events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • one factual manual on cluster development was created, which contained the expediency, mechanism and features of cluster organization; • a steering group for cluster development has been formed, which operates under the Cabinet of Ministers; • published a book on competitiveness «Our competitive future: building a knowledge-based economy» (1998); • a map of clusters was created, 154 clusters were identified, from 8 to 18 in each region, depending on the geographical location, development and specialization of each region. 	To start the clustering process by studying the specialization of agro-industrial complex by regions, determining the main criteria for distribution and on this basis to create a map of clusters of Ukraine. Another important step is to form an approach to increasing competitiveness as one of the priorities in a market economy, emphasizing its importance and identifying opportunities for change on the path to leadership in the industry.
Switzerland	Objective: to stimulate innovation and development of all regions. Measures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vinnvaxt is the world's best example of cluster-based innovation; • Visanu program (strengthening clusters regardless of their location, which is based on the dissemination of knowledge, creating the most favorable conditions for clustering); • regional cluster program (stimulating the implementation of clustering, export, marketing and cooperation initiatives with research institutions. 	Borrow and adapt innovation development programs – the basis for structural change, stimulation and motivation to implement new initiatives within the agro-industrial clusters, development of marketing and logistics in them, the definition of exports as a promising area of cooperation.
Japan	Purpose: intensification of business activity, increase of competitiveness. Measures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 programs for the formation of the clustering development base; • Regional Bureaus for Economy, Trade and Industry (RBETI) have been established to work directly with small and medium-sized businesses; • encouraging the expansion of clusters in the direction of cooperation with universities, the creation of new venture enterprises. 	Create a bureau or other structure to attract small and medium-sized businesses, help adapt to new conditions of cooperation, promote clustering ideas among small producers as a basis for the formation of new regional clusters.
Austria	Objective: to join forces in the economy to adapt to EU membership. Measures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • strategic development program based on education, qualification training and marketing placement of clusters; • providing special support to small and medium enterprises; • programs to increase the motivation of cluster participants, their skills. 	Create a program to increase the motivation of participants, their interest in clustering, and in the future – training to improve the skills of agricultural workers in order to overcome major problems in the industry.

Source: Development of authors by sources [4–10].

ture the system of state and public administration of agriculture and the social sphere of the village on the basis of decentralization and self-government which demands in-depth analysis of world experience and the possibility of adapting clusters for the Ukrainian agro-industrial complex (Table 1).

To model innovation clusters in the agro-industrial complex, it is necessary to ensure the following areas: democratization of economic interests of cluster stakeholders; availability of financial and innovative resources; establishment of infrastructural support; development of vertical-horizontal intra-cluster communication [4; 9].

Cluster development has always been difficult. An important complication of its functioning will be that the probability of obtaining profit for business entities will be low, if the organization of cluster initiatives is not introduced [6; 8; 10]. The potential risks and barriers to cluster development for the agro-industrial complex of Ukraine can be:

1. The difficulty of choosing winners. Creating a sectoral cluster program requires in-depth knowledge of the region and its economic problems. To do this, it is necessary to perform a detailed study of the region, determine its specialization, problems and prospects. Due to their participation in the development of agriculture in the country, the regions of Ukraine are not homogeneous. For example, the central regions are the «granaries» of Ukraine, the southern regions specialize in melons and fruits due to climatic features, while in the eastern regions of Ukraine the share of agro-industrial complex is quite small in the structure of the economy.

2. Lack of material infrastructure, lag of technological support. The lack of infrastructure hinders capital investment. Until the agro-industrial complex takes the first steps towards modernization and competitiveness, investors will not be confident in the feasibility of investing capital and the possibility of making a profit.

3. Difficulty of entrepreneurs' access to capital. The duration of clusters is directly dependent on the resource and administrative capacity of local areas and enterprises. The emergence and commercialization of know-how requires resources and capital. But investors often prefer «new economy» companies to low-tech companies and innovation hubs in more remote locations that are difficult to organize and maintain.

4. Imperfect technological and innovative market segments. The activities of clusters depend on local institutions in many areas, which they cannot implement themselves or receive from other enterprises. They use regional institutions to obtain information and assistance in technology upgrades, economic education, securities trading, education and training at all levels in their fields. During the independence of Ukraine, research centers and advisory services in some regions have lost their position as leaders in consulting and support, especially for experts on the work of the agro-industrial complex. The only thing that keeps these structures going is the interest of the European Union in the development of Ukraine as a potentially powerful food producer.

5. Regional isolation and limitations. While financial capital is a source of resources within a cluster, profitability is highly dependent on the ability to absorb new information and ideas from greater distances.

6. Lack of managerial experience and communications. Businesses will not be formed or developed in communities where skills are low and administrative resources do not meet the needs of employers. The country's workforce skills are the «gene pool» of a successful economy.

7. Businesses that create a cluster later may not be able to compete. Those clusters that were created earlier have advantages over those that joined later. The first clusters on the market conserve resources, provide innovative infrastructure, institutional support and have a socially oriented network, which is not possible for new or smaller clusters.

The information structure of the agro-industrial economy under the influence of the innovation cycles of the sixth technological system in the future will strive to achieve the appropriate level of technological development. In this case, the trend of forming comprehensively interacting agro-industrial clusters and technological platforms, on the basis of which the agro-industrial information system will be able to actively develop, is recommended to be developed as follows (Fig. 1).

According to the authors, the sequence of creating clusters in the agro-industrial sphere of Ukraine should include a stage of preliminary analysis and specification of optimal territories and enterprises, which concentrates the study of existing potential of regions, production traditions, study

Figure 1. Integrated development of innovation clusters and technology platforms in agriculture

Source: Development of authors by sources [1; 4; 10].

of production structure. The process of modeling the participants of the innovation industry cluster, which can be depicted in Fig. 2.

State regulation of innovative development of agro-industrial complex on the basis of cluster model should be carried out in order to achieve its most effective socio-economic development, increase the competitiveness of agricultural products and improve its quality. In the process of such regulation economic support should be provided to

agricultural enterprises, which are major producers of agricultural products, to ensure the required level of profitability of farms in adverse market conditions, as well as the production of such quality products that meet consumer needs and thus maintain social stability of society [2; 5; 7]

Effective implementation of the innovation function in the development of agriculture, According to the authors, requires the formation of an effective institutional environment, adequate to global tech-

Figure 2. The process of modeling the participants of the innovation industry cluster

Source: Developed by the authors.

Table 2. The role of participants in the institutional environment of innovative development of agriculture using the cluster model

Participant	The main role
Agricultural enterprises	Carry out socialized innovative agricultural production in the form of clusters
Investors	They invest in socialized innovative agricultural production
State and local authorities	Establish institutional conditions, determine social, agricultural, innovation policy, act as guarantors between participants in the innovation process in clusters
Scientific organizations and universities	Carry out research activities, fulfill orders for R&D, train specialists with innovative thinking, are engaged in education
Innovators	Independently develop innovative projects, provide support in the implementation of innovative cluster projects
Intermediaries and end users	Based on consumer utility, make rational decisions on the selection and production of better and cheaper agricultural products

Source: Development of authors by sources [2; 5; 10].

nological transformation, which will serve as a basis for directing the innovative development of agriculture (Table 2).

The following blocks should become the key institutional components of innovative development of agro-industrial complex in cluster model:

- effective state institutions, reasonable state agricultural and innovation policy;
- production and consumer cooperation;
- development of intellectual capital through education and increase of spiritual values;
- institutionalization, clustering and socialization of the village;
- change of role and reorientation of interests of agrarian business;

– creating conditions for attracting investment in agriculture;

– change in the technological structure of agriculture;

– the necessary and sufficient level of value added obtained by restoring the equivalence of exchange and parity of pricing.

In order to integrate scientific and technical, organizational competencies and intellectual and resource potentials of agro-industrial complex, it is progressive to use scientific system integrator as a modern form of management of innovative development of society, which forms innovative, scientific, investment, production leaders them to achieve the goals of intra- and inter-cluster interaction

Figure 3. Modeling of the «Information and resource center» (IRC) as a scientific integrator of the agro-industrial cluster

Source: Developed by the authors.

based on the creation of competitive advantages in the long run. At the state level, the system integrator in the cluster model of innovative development of agro-industrial complex can be innovative regional centers as points of support, growth or similar in their properties institutes of innovative development of agro-industrial complex, around which clusters in different industry segments will form. RICs are able to effectively play the role of the core in clusters, concentrating all the key competencies that are needed for innovative development of agriculture in the country (Fig. 3).

The implementation of the cluster model of innovative development of agro-industrial complex is based on determining the relationships between cluster participants and the organization of interac-

tion, which will lead to the creation of an adequate innovation environment. In general, the use of scientific system integrator in the management of cluster interaction ensures the creation of an attractive investment climate, increasing demand for innovation, increasing the rate of commercialization of innovation, etc. [2; 7; 10]. However, in general, sharing the position of [4; 8] on the need to implement in the process of modernization of the strategy of humanized society, we believe that clustering should be methodologically based, on the one hand, on forming an active nonprofit sector that will meet social and spiritual needs, and, on the other hand, on the development of a competitive commercial sector that will meet the material needs of society. As a result, a synergistic effect of the coordination of interests

Table 3. Directions of use of financial resources in the process of modeling the agro-industrial cluster

Sources of financial resources	Capital			Investments in the non-productive sphere	Consumption costs	Financial reserve
	Direct investment	Venture capital	Portfolio investments			
Profit	+	-	-	+	+	+
Depreciation deductions	+	-	-	+	-	+
Bank loans available to the company	+	-	-	+	+	-
Proceeds from the sale of securities (added capital)	-	+	+	-	-	+
Shares and other contributions	+	-	-	+	+	+
Subsidies and loans	+	+	-	+	+	-

Source: Development of authors by sources [2; 5; 8].

Table 4. Characteristics of funding sources in the process of cluster modeling

Types of financing	Evaluation criteria			
	Accessibility	Capacity	Efficiency of use	Risk level
Development funds	Maximum	Insignificant (proportions of distribution of profit on consumption and accumulation)	Maximum	Minimum
Issue of shares	Satisfactory (for profitable enterprises)	Significant (attractiveness of shares)	Significant (dividends on shares)	Satisfactory (share capital structure)
Consolidated funds	Satisfactory (integration capability of the enterprise)	Satisfactory (terms of consolidated contracts)		
Credits and loans	Low (for highly profitable and reliable enterprises)	Maximum	Low (credit rate)	Low (loan agreement terms)
Government loans	Minimum (enterprise priority)	Maximum	Maximum (cheap resource)	Minimum
Public investment	Minimum (special status of the enterprise)	Maximum	Maximum	Minimum

Source: Authors' development.

will be achieved if the strategies of each of these sectors are implemented simultaneously with the strategy of effective partnership based on the identification and further interaction of certain areas of sectoral control.

Thus, a comprehensive solution to the problem of innovative development of agriculture is the formation of a cluster model of innovative development at both state and regional levels. In the table 3 the most probable directions of use of different sources types of cluster innovative elements financing are presented, and table 4 describes the different sources of funding, taking into account the criteria of availability, potential capacity, efficiency, level of risk.

The cluster approach will allow agribusiness companies to focus on everything they know and do best, they will not have to do things they cannot do, they will also benefit from synergies. Innovation clusters are an effective model of interaction between science, education and production, a connecting link between the developer and consumer of innovation, between a scientific idea and its practical implementation. Therefore, the development of a comprehensive scientific concept of the formation of mechanisms of clustering in the agro–industrial complex in the conditions of European integration with the countries of the European community is an immediate scientific problem, the solution of which will allow differentiating the emphasis in the use of regulatory mechanisms of state regulation, determining the goals and nature of state support for the development of the agricultural sector on the basis of cluster partnership.

Conclusions

Modeling of innovative cluster development of agro–industrial complex in the conditions of globalization and digitalization will have the following advantages: possibility of joint use of the united capitals and acceleration of introduction of innovations; joint use of resources, logistics, savings on their acquisition and maintenance; effective specialization of enterprises in accordance with the region, scale of activities and features of the functioning of each individual enterprise of agro–industrial complex; division of regions according to available resources and capacity of enterprises, avoidance of unfair competition; gaining profits from clustering and eliminating shortcomings caused by non-profit enterprises, reducing some transformation

costs; reduction and distribution of risks resulting from mutually beneficial cooperation and positive synergies; increasing the level of profitability of the Ukrainian agro–industrial complex; increasing the resilience of individual enterprises and clusters as a whole; establishment of long–term communications along the logistics chain, including links between the public and business sectors. Further research will be modeling the institutional environment of Ukrainian innovation clusters taking into account the state of war and the instability of the external environment.

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Дані про авторів

Кукса Ігор Миколайович,

д.е.н., професор, професор кафедри економічної кібернетики і системного аналізу, Харківський національний економічний університет імені Семена Куз-

неця, м. Харків, Україна

Левків Галина Ярославівна,

д.е.н., доцент, доцент кафедри менеджменту, Національний університет ветеринарної медицини та біотехнологій імені Степана Гжицького, Львів, Україна

Телічко Наталія Олександрівна,

к.е.н., доцент, доцент кафедри менеджменту, Одеський державний аграрний університет, Одеса, Україна

Data about the authors

Ihor Kuksa,

Doctor of Economics Sciences, Professor, Professor of the Economic Cybernetics and System Analysis Department Simon Kuznets Kharkiv National University of Economics, Kharkiv, Ukraine

Halyna Levkiv,

Doctor of Economics Sciences, Associate Professor, Professor of Department of Management, Stepan Gzhytskyi National University of Veterinary Medicine and Biotechnologies, Lviv, Ukraine

Nataliia Telichko,

PhD (Economics), Associate Professor, Associate Professor of Department of Management, Odessa State Agrarian University, Odessa, Ukraine